

5 MAIN METHODS OF FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the idea of forming spiritual culture among primary school students in the family, "mahalla" and general education schools.*

Keywords: *spiritual-cultural, moral, humanitarianism, spiritual-moral education, spiritual-moral understanding, enlightenment.*

Introduction

Educating young people, who are the future of our country, and raising them to be highly moral based on the requirements of the times is an urgent problem of today. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "This should be included in the educational process in the lower grades". This encourages every student, pedagogue or generation to develop spiritually and morally, ideologically fighting against any destructive ideas and ideologies is a responsible approach.

It is known that the process of education is a complex process that requires uniqueness. It is the duty and responsibility of our society to form the worldview of the young generation based on modern knowledge, human faith, moral and spiritual qualities characteristic of the people.

Morality and spirituality are interrelated concepts, and spirituality is an integral part of them, and it has a high impact on the perfection of a person. Therefore, spirituality is an integral, interrelated, dialectical character in spiritual and moral education, and it is important in the spiritual and moral formation of a person. Spirituality is actually the most powerful factor of man and all beings, spirituality gives him strength and spiritual nourishment. The concept of spirituality As the first President I.A. Karimov said, "Spirituality is not a gift of fate. In order to develop spirituality in the human heart, it is necessary to work with it - heart, conscience, mind and hands."

Every nation is strong not only with its wealth, but also with its high level of spirituality and culture. To restore and improve our national values from the first days of Uzbekistan's independence the national education system, bringing up a mature generation, gave great importance to the education of the spirit of patriotism and love for the motherland.

An important pedagogical task of personality formation is an active life position in students, a conscientious attitude to social duty, unity, speech and action, not tolerating deviations from moral standards. Our teachers want to deeply study all the rich heritage of the Uzbek people, to return to our origins, to understand the depth and greatness of cultural and spiritual, the heritage and cultural achievements of our great ancestors who made a great contribution to the world, forming a careful attitude to each one's own past, it is necessary to clearly understand the need for the generation to study and join the noble national and religious traditions and at the same time modern values. Civilization and spirituality, political maturity and activity of the future generation and population are the basis for building our education policy.

The Main Purpose

In order to formation and development of spiritual culture in primary classes, he purposefully started the work that is being carried out in the initial stages of raising our spirituality, which is considered relevant today. Spirituality and ethics, in turn, require the organization of the educational process. It is known that education is carried out through state and public institutions specially organized for the purposeful preparation of the young generation to live in society. There are factors that have a direct and indirect effect on development and encouragement, spiritual culture in society, raising a mature generation:

1. The role of the family in the formation and development of a unique national personality, the values and spirituality of each nation, a generation with a high spiritual culture is invaluable in raising a well-rounded person, because the purest and purest feelings of a person in his first life are concepts and ideas. . It is formed primarily in the family.

The family should be the foundation of such holy concepts as goodness and love. Kindness, nobility, kindness, honor and dignity that determine the natural character, the nature and worldview of the child: goodness and nobility, kindness, honor and dignity should be decided in the family.

2. Another important factor in the formation of our spiritual culture is the growing "mahalla" environment. Realization of identity as a social and national value The first manifestations of the concept of kindness and honesty in today's society are formed in the "mahalla", in the social environment.

3. Pre-school education and general school education are another part of formation of spiritual culture. If it is closely related to the continuous process, the requirements of its norms and education are properly implemented, it will not fail.

It is enough to remember the following words of A. Avloniy: "Education is for us either life or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster." its influence is clearly expressed and refined, and the expression of its concepts in the mind of the reader is considered as a continuation of the stages of the formation of spiritual culture. it is our ability to teach moral values, aesthetics, hygiene and discipline, because reading is one of the leading factors of spirituality.

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Books are a tool that has a great impact on enriching the spiritual world of a person."

If the love for books was formed from the elementary grades, then our great figures. They can become worthy heirs of A. Navoiy, M. Bobur, A. Temur, M.Ulug'bek and many others, and respect for the spiritual heritage of our ancestors and interest in studying them will increase once again.

4. Mass media also play an important role in forming the spiritual culture of the young generation. Especially for our children, age-appropriate and individual shows with different themes, interesting and educational films and cartoons, Demonstrations to enrich knowledge, multimedia lessons, of course, give the child spiritual nourishment.

5. Classroom and extracurricular activities, various entertainment in elementary grades parks, trips to different places, theatrical performances, clubs and sports events also help the child develop as a well-rounded person.

Problem Statement

Launching of the "Five Initiatives" project of the President Sh.M. It is no exaggeration to say that Mirziyoyev is focused on supporting young people and developing their capabilities and solving current issues. Support modern reading, sports, science and art, computer literacy and communication technologies introduced as gifted and innovative, all mentioned in the five initiatives are seen as a factor in the rise of our culture.

Spiritual education in the general secondary education system as stated in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the implementation of the approval of the concept of continuous spiritual and moral education and its measures" No. 31.12.1059 , especially primary education has a special place. This, in turn, contributes to the expansion of moral and cultural skills, the enrichment of spiritual relations with peers, the development of social competences and necessary qualities.

Spiritual culture is the process of human perception of the external world through inner mood, freedom. The formation of spiritual culture should be based on national and universal values.

The most important thing in raising young people spiritually is a healthy family environment. If this family has universal human values such as hospitality, honesty, friendship, loyalty, kindness, then the first stages of spirituality are formed. The formation of spiritual and moral education in students requires the development of their spiritual world, consciousness, moral qualities, personal qualities and behavior. Moral education of students, especially in elementary school students, child feels spiritual influence in the family, among peers, at school, on the street. Teachers educate the young generation, teach them to be compassionate and kind to their country, people, parents and others.

Various spiritual and educational events were held by the teachers of the primary classes according to the abilities and talents of the students in the formation of the spiritual culture of the students.

The bottom line is:

1. Spiritual activity should be interesting, purposeful and meaningful depending on the age;
2. Ability to create a healthy environment for students to acquire spiritual and educational knowledge;
3. Spiritual and educational activity should be reliable and diverse;
4. The process of explaining and promoting that moral concepts depend on a person to have qualities;
5. In the course of continuous education, conversations are held with students on the topics "My family", "My country", "I love my country", "I am a true child of my child";
6. By organizing "Patriotic" meetings with the military on January 14, it is necessary to create love for the Motherland, people, family, and spiritual culture in them.
7. Concepts on moral issues have educational value

Spiritual culture can be organized in primary schools in the following ways:

1. **Interpretation** - verbal emotional impact on students;
2. **Admonition** - if the pupil gives purposeful advice in a state of loyalty and kindness, the student will accept it;
3. **Assurance** – a great help in educating students in moral consciousness.

In conclusion

We recommend that primary school teachers pay attention to the following in order to create a spiritual culture in the classroom.

When Alisher Navoi said "People of meaning", he meant a perfect person who has real enlightenment. Enlightenment means knowledge and spirituality. So, enlightenment is a concept closely related to the spiritual world of a person. Spirituality is the strength of humanity, nation, society, and state, therefore, the faster the spiritual culture of society and people develops, the easier it is for the country to develop. Undoubtedly, our great thinker is Alisher Navoiy himself has a high spirituality, so he is a "Spiritual nation." invincible."

World experience shows that countries such as Germany and Japan occupy a special place in the twenties with the enlightenment of their people. A spiritually poor nation will never be rich. People who do not know their rights do not understand the glory of the people, do not want to understand the power of their laws, the system of spirituality and enlightenment in such a country will be trampled on, it will have no place in the world community. It should be noted that the concept of spirituality also includes the concept of enlightenment.

The attention paid to our youth, all the efforts made by our compatriots are aimed at raising our morale. So, in return, it is our highest duty to raise a young generation with high spirituality.

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